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Assuring workplace training quality in firms: Insights into the work of inspectors in the dual Swiss VET system

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ABSTRACT

The quality of workplace training in firms is a key factor in both apprentices' development of skills and the prevention of dropouts in corporatist dual vocational education and training (VET) systems. This article addresses the governance practices at the micro level of VET in a French-speaking Swiss canton by examining how the legal framework for quality inspection is put into practice. Based on interviews with cantonal inspectors who control and promote quality training in firms, the article focuses on how they adapt the legal framework to their conditions of action. Due to the high workload, inspectors seldom visit firms regularly enough to address problems and conflicts at an early stage to prevent dropouts. Empowering apprentices, who are often reluctant to defend their rights and ask inspectors to intervene, is thus an important measure. Given the trainers' lack of both qualifications and time for training, inspectors also prioritise guidance over control. Withdrawing a firm's training licence is rarely initiated, however, as it is an arduous process and often not feasible. The article highlights the impact that actors, such as inspectors, have at the micro level of VET and how coordination with trainers and apprentices defines how a legal framework is implemented.

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Introduction

The quality of workplace training in corporatist dual vocational education and training (VET) systems has been receiving increased attention in VET research (Af Burén and Schweri 2024; Negrini et al. 2016). The value of the qualifications obtained in such programmes greatly depends on the quality of workplace training the firm provides, since apprentices generally spend more time at work than at the VET schools. However, the assurance of workplace training quality takes place in a complex system, with the stakeholders and characteristics of the VET system at the macro (the country or region), meso (e.g. the firm as the training institution), and micro (e.g. the actors involved in the training process) levels all contributing to quality (Fischer et al. 2014; Fuller and Unwin 2011). The creation, maintenance, or transformation of any framework in such multilevel VET systems thus depends on how contributing social actors coordinate their actions both

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within and across the different levels – an issue that is central to the educational governance approach (Altrichter 2010), which has already been utilised in the field of VET research (Strebel, Engelage, and Baumeler 2019).

A common critique of educational governance research is that studies often focus on governance phenomena at the macro and meso levels, while frequently neglecting the practices and coordination between actors at the micro level – even though it is precisely these practices that bring governance to life (Langer and Brüsemeister 2019). Such practices are central to understanding, for example, how a legal framework or formal rules defined at the macro or meso levels are implemented, how they may be modified, and why these changes occur, including their implications within the specific area of governance.

Building on this critique, this article contributes to research on educational governance by shedding light on the actual practices of governance at the micro level in the area of quality assurance within the Swiss VET system. Drawing on a qualitative interview study with Swiss inspectors responsible for inspecting and promoting workplace training quality on behalf of a cantonal VET authority in a French-speaking canton, the article asks how inspectors concretely implement the legal framework defined at the macro and meso levels of the Swiss VET system in the context of inspections. More specifically, it explores the conditions of action at the micro level that inspectors encounter when applying the legal framework and consequently how inspectors may adapt this framework to fit their specific context, particularly when coordinating with trainers and apprentices who are directly involved in the inspection and promotion of workplace training quality. In doing so, the article provides insights into how inspectors' adaptations of the legal framework to their conditions of action shape the way inspections of workplace training quality are practised.

The article is structured as follows. First, the context section introduces the Swiss VET system, focusing on the regulation of inspection and workplace training quality as well as research into the latter, which provides insights into inspectors' conditions of action. The theory section discusses what dimensions of quality may be considered and how inspectors might adapt the legal framework of inspection to their conditions of action. Then, the article presents the methodology of the qualitative interviews conducted with inspectors from the selected canton. The findings section analyses the inspectors' conditions of action and the adaptations they make when applying the legal framework for inspection. Finally, the discussion highlights how the educational governance approach contributes to the study of inspection and the promotion of workplace training quality in dual VET systems and what this implies for further research.

Context

The Swiss VET system and the regulation of inspection and workplace training quality

Switzerland is internationally renowned for its low youth unemployment rate¹ and, like Germany, its high-quality VET system (Deissinger and Gonon 2021). After 11 years of compulsory schooling, young people aged 15–16 have to decide whether to continue academic, general, or vocational education. Two-thirds of young

people enter VET, mostly provided in the form of dual apprenticeships lasting two, three, or four years (OFS 2024a). The 230 dual VET programmes combine one to two days per week of theoretical vocational and general education in a VET school with three to four days of practical training in a firm. Switzerland is composed of three language regions, and dual VET is historically more anchored in the German-speaking rather than in the French- and Italian-speaking regions (Bonoli and Vorpe 2022).

The general purpose of VET, according to the federal Vocational and Professional Education and Training Act (VPETA),² is the personal and professional development of learners and their integration into society and the labour market. VET should also enable firms to become more competitive. The purpose of educational programmes ('what should be achieved') is often used as a quality criterion (Negrini et al. 2016). The Swiss VET system builds on a strong quality assurance framework to ensure these objectives are met.

All vocational programmes are issued by the State Secretary for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI) and lead to nationally recognised certificates and diplomas. However, the content is defined and regularly reviewed by the relevant trade associations, taking into account sector-specific needs and developments (SERI 2023). To assure quality workplace training, each programme specifies in an ordinance the qualifications required of trainers and the maximum number of apprentices per trainer. The ordinance also outlines the occupational competences to be covered during workplace training, the regular evaluation and feedback to be provided to apprentices, and the examination at the end of the programme. For each programme, training plans outline the structure and content of the training that firms must implement and adapt to their workplace environment. All of these regulations are relevant for inspectors of workplace training quality.

The Vocational and Professional Education and Training Act (art. 24) and the related Vocational and Professional Education and Training Ordinance (art. 11)³ require firms to be inspected by the cantonal VET authorities to ensure quality. Switzerland is composed of 26 cantons, each with its own cantonal government. Cantonal VET authorities are responsible for issuing training permits to firms and withdrawing them if the training proves unsatisfactory. They must also ensure that the legal provisions in the apprenticeship contract and during the apprenticeship are observed by the contracting parties. To participate in a dual VET programme, young people sign an apprenticeship contract directly with a firm that provides training. The VET school to which they are assigned does not have a role in assuring the quality of their workplace training. Cantonal authorities charge inspectors with supervisory tasks to fulfil these legal obligations, which also include promoting training quality in firms and offering advice and support to firms and apprentices if questions, difficulties, or conflicts arise.

Cantonal VET authorities organise inspections (to some extent) autonomously (Duemmler and Caprani 2021). They may employ general inspectors or cooperate with trade associations representing the occupational sector's interests to employ occupation-specific inspectors. The latter usually serve on a part-time basis in addition to their main occupational activity. Some, such as the canton in this study, use both models. Inspectors are required to have significant vocational experience, including in training apprentices, and certifications beyond the initial VET diploma. Cantonal VET authorities support inspectors to ensure that legal requirements are met.

Although the specific terms of reference for inspectors are defined by the cantonal VET authorities, a study showed that there are similarities across cantons in terms of how inspectors concretely fulfil their mission of inspecting and promoting the quality of workplace training (Duemmler and Caprani 2021). When a firm applies for a training licence, inspectors have to conduct two site visits. The purpose of the first visit is to check that the trainer has the required qualifications, and that the firm's human resources and organisational and technical infrastructure allows for training according to the VET programme. A second visit is scheduled a year later to assess whether training is being provided according to the training plan and whether apprentices are being guided to acquire the required competences. Inspectors have to write a report and provide their recommendation to the cantonal authority on whether the firm should receive or keep a training licence.

Cantons vary when it comes to the terms of reference they provide to inspectors regarding how to follow up on the inspection of a licenced firm (Duemmler and Caprani 2021). Sometimes, inspectors only have to intervene if apprentices, parents, trainers, or the cantonal VET authority call them in case of problems. In such cantons, inspectors are responsible for overseeing a large number of firms and apprentices – up to 2,000 per inspector. Some cantons invest greater personnel resources, and inspectors must regularly visit apprentices and firms to check whether legal requirements are being met (Duemmler and Caprani 2021). In any case, all inspectors have to provide support to apprentices and guidance to firms by setting up measures and deadlines to improve quality and ensure that the legal requirements, in particular the ordinance of the VET programme, are fulfilled. In cases of persistent non-compliance or breaches of labour legislation, inspectors have to report the problems to the cantonal authority and can advise to withdraw the training licence.

In the canton featured here, regular preventive visits to firms are recommended, but not compulsory, according to the terms of reference for inspectors. During any visit, however, inspectors always have to check whether trainers have the required qualifications, whether a training plan is in place, and whether regular feedback is provided to apprentices. This canton is also more restrictive regarding training licences. Licences are issued for a period of six years, and inspectors have to visit firms as part of the renewal process. Moreover, inspectors have to visit new apprentices at the beginning of their apprenticeship at their vocational school or industry-specific branch course to explain their supporting role in the event that problems arise. When company training is compromised, or in cases of contract termination, inspectors must support apprentices in finding a new apprenticeship position.

Research findings related to workplace training quality

While research has documented that workplace training quality in Swiss VET is generally rather high, studies have also highlighted that some firms struggle to provide quality training (Af Burén and Schweri 2024; Negrini et al. 2016). Firms might neglect the intended training plan, give insufficient guidance to apprentices, or fail to provide access to varied and complex tasks. A study with trainers found that they were often torn between their roles as workers and trainers, noting that they could seldom devote as much time to training as they would like because their role was not sufficiently

recognised by the firm (Lamamra and Duc 2021). Many trainers would also like to receive more training to deal with the complexities and challenges of the role (Wenger and Lamamra 2023). Research has also documented that trainers' perceptions of apprentices can be placed on a continuum between worker and learner, with respective implications for the training provided (Besozzi 2024). Certain trainers stress the rapid development of apprentices' autonomy, some strongly emphasise vocational skills, and others focus on guiding apprentices into the adult world. There are also those trainers who are not particularly interested in apprentices' personal and professional development. A study on the perception of quality in the Swiss VET system further revealed that trainers generally place more emphasis on the pre-qualifications or motivation of apprentices or their acquisition of competences, whereas apprentices emphasise the quality of learning opportunities or the guidance received during training (Sauli, Wenger, and Berger 2021; Wenger et al. 2019). Despite their expectations in terms of training quality, apprentices often try to adapt to the training contexts provided to them and frequently accept poor working and training conditions if their negotiations with trainers are not successful (Caprani, Duemmler, and Felder 2020).

However, low-quality training in firms is not only associated with lower success rates on final exams (Af Burén and Schweri 2024) but also with higher rates of early withdrawal from apprenticeship programmes (Negrini et al. 2016). In Switzerland, one-fourth of apprentices end their contract early (OFS 2023). Although poor training quality is not the only reason for dropouts and many young people later continue their training in another firm or occupation (Stalder and Carigiet 2014), they often experience a difficult period in their lives because of the stress involved and the resulting fear of reintegrating into the working world (Duc et al. 2014).

These different research findings suggest that inspectors might be confronted with complex problems related to the quality of workplace training because they have to strike a balance between the training expectations and needs of apprentices, the trainers' attitudes towards apprentices, and the working conditions under which training can be provided. The French-speaking canton in which this study is situated has approximately 17,000 apprentices, representing about eight percent of all apprentices in Switzerland.⁴ It is of particular interest as it is located in a region with a high rate of premature contract terminations, affecting approximately one-third of apprenticeships (OFS 2023). Depending on their school marks, many young people have also long been attracted to other general and academic educational programmes. The cantonal VET authority has therefore resolved to make apprenticeships more attractive and effective. One recently introduced measure is a project to improve the inspection of workplace training quality in firms. The cantonal authority funded this research in this context, aiming to develop recommendations to improve inspectors' work and strengthen the quality assurance system.

Theoretical framework: inspection of workplace training quality

Since the educational governance approach is a general framework that was not specifically developed to study the inspection and promotion of workplace training quality, this section will first discuss the dimensions of workplace training quality that inspectors

might need to address in their work. From an educational governance perspective, the focus then shifts to conceptualising the conditions under which actors at the micro level operate when implementing a legal framework defined at the meso and macro levels, such as in the case of inspections within the Swiss VET system.

Different models of workplace training quality in VET agree that workplace training quality is multidimensional and that input, process, and output factors⁵ can be distinguished at all levels of the VET system (Böhn and Deutscher 2021; Fischer et al. 2014; Sauli, Wenger, and Berger 2021; Tynjälä 2013). Input factors, understood as prerequisites for quality, generally include the institutional framework of the VET system, as well as the organisational characteristics of the firm and its learning environment (Fuller and Unwin 2011). Key elements include the quality of the training plan; the material, organisational, and human resources of the firm; the working climate; the qualifications of the training staff; the available training and learning aids; and entry requirements for apprentices (Böhn and Deutscher 2021). Process quality refers to the training and learning process and includes work tasks and their characteristics (e.g. variety, relevance), the quality of the social interactions between apprentices and other employees, and the educational mediation by trainers, such as guidance, feedback, or adherence to the training plan (Böhn and Deutscher 2021). Output quality refers to what is achieved during or after the training, such as passing exams, dropout rates, apprentices' satisfaction with training, development of competences, and career orientation (Fischer et al. 2014).

Given the inspectors' terms of reference presented in the context section and their intermediate position in the Swiss VET system (Sauli 2022), all these levels and dimensions play a role in their work. They are responsible for ensuring that quality standards and regulations at the macro level of the VET system – for instance, concerning the training plans or the training conditions – are respected when authorising a firm, as well as during the apprenticeship. Inspectors must thus supervise input quality (e.g. the qualification of trainers) and (at least after one year, or if there is a complaint or a preventive visit) control and promote process quality (e.g. the relationship between apprentices and trainers), while output (e.g. dissatisfaction with training, lack of skill development, dropout) serves as an indicator that quality may be lacking and that inspectors must intervene (by, e.g. guiding trainers and apprentices, initiating the withdrawal of the training licence, etc.).

The concept of recontextualisation from the educational governance literature (Magnus 2019) offers not only an understanding of how inspectors implement inspections of workplace training quality according to such a legal framework but also how they might adapt their terms of reference to their specific conditions of action. Recontextualisation assumes that actors, who are situated in a multilevel system, have a certain freedom or autonomy to respond at their own level to requirements formulated at the higher level(s). Although they act in a context that is defined (more or less directly) by the higher level(s) (for instance, the law or the training plans), they reinterpret this framework within their own context when putting it into practice (Magnus 2019). This concept originates from Giddens' structuration theory, which attributes to individuals a capacity to act that is not entirely determined by structures, even though structures provide the rules and resources (e.g. status, money, things, time) that enable and constrain individual action (Giddens 1984). In this sense, structures enable practices but are reproduced through actors' routinised actions – a dynamic referred to as the duality of structure.

For inspectors, this means acting within a context where the instructions set at higher levels are present and guide their actions; however, these requirements may be reinterpreted in light of the conditions for action at their level and the resources available to them. In other words, the requirements may be adapted to the context, potentially generating more specific – or even entirely new – tasks, duties, or responsibilities necessary to fulfil their work obligations (Magnus 2019). It is important to note that actors may either accept the institutional demands imposed by higher levels or exert pressure to modify these requirements if they prove impossible to implement. However, it is not only the higher levels or the context for action that matter (ibid.). The lower levels and their actors – in this case, trainers in firms and apprentices – may also provide feedback on how requirements and standards can be put into practice. Since inspectors work directly with trainers and apprentices, they can take into account the consequences of their actions for these actors. As a result, not only institutional but also contextual and interactional logics of action can influence the implementation of a legal or administrative framework (ibid.), such as the inspection of workplace training quality. To sum up, despite quality characteristics at the macro and meso levels of the VET system being an important condition for assuring that firms or trainers provide good training (Deissinger 1996), the micro levels must be taken into account, as their actors can redefine their tasks and responsibilities (Büchter 2014).

Research methods

This article is based on a qualitative study conducted in 2020/2021 on behalf of the VET authority of the canton featured here. In a first step, the federal and cantonal legal framework for inspection in the Swiss VET system was analysed to understand how inspection is meant to be implemented. In addition, five exploratory interviews conducted with cantonal VET managers – who support and guide the inspectors in their work – along with relevant official documents, like the terms of reference for inspectors, were analysed to better understand the legal framework for inspection. All of this information was incorporated in the context section of the article.

The analysis that follows mainly draws on the 20 subsequent semi-structured interviews with inspectors who carry out quality control and guidance in direct contact with apprentices and trainers in firms. The overall aim of the interviews was to understand how inspectors put the inspection and promotion of workplace training quality into practice, what conditions of action they face, and how they cope with these conditions when applying the legal framework for inspection.

The interview guide contained questions on how inspectors perceive and experience their mission of inspection and promotion of workplace training quality, and particularly their different terms of reference. Questions were asked about how inspectors practice preventive visits, how they support firms and apprentices in case of problems or propose measures to firms to improve training quality, and how they proceed if they have to evaluate whether firms can obtain or keep a training licence. In addition to the resources at their disposal, such as time, personnel, and technical support, the interview questions also covered the conditions (including problems and constraints) that inspectors face in their work when interacting with trainers and apprentices, and how they cope with them. All these questions are particularly relevant for the analysis presented here.

During a meeting, the 68 inspectors of the French-speaking Swiss canton (a majority of whom, 57, were employed by trade organisations) were invited to take part in the study on a voluntary basis. Suggestions from VET managers on who else to contact to ensure diversity were used to complete the sample. The study guaranteed participant anonymity, and informed consent was obtained from all the interviewed inspectors.⁶ The one-hour interviews were conducted via video conference due to COVID-19 restrictions and were subsequently transcribed and anonymised. The aim was to obtain a diverse sample of inspectors with respect to sex, age, vocational field, work experience, workload, and type of inspectors in order to ensure the inclusion of a range of perspectives.

- Participants: 20 inspectors (11 men, 9 women)
- Age range: 35 to 65 years
- Vocational fields represented: construction and building, commerce and sales, hospitality and skilled trades, industry and mechanics, health and social services
- Experience as inspectors: 1 to 20 years
- Workload: average of 55% full-time equivalent; range: 20 to 80%
- Type of inspectors: 18 occupation-specific inspectors, 2 general inspectors

The occupation-specific inspectors were, in parallel to their work as inspectors, active in their occupation as self-employed workers, employees, branch course instructors, or examiners. All had received further training after their VET diploma and had many years of vocational experience, including training positions. The cantonal authority stipulates that inspectors employed at 80% are responsible for about 500 apprentices. However, the number of apprentices assigned to the inspectors interviewed ranged from 350 to 650 for an 80% workload. To best preserve participant anonymity, minimal individual information is provided here and in the analysis, limited to instances where these characteristics were deemed relevant.

For this article, the interviews with inspectors were analysed in depth using NVivo. For the thematic coding (Kuckartz 2018), initial codes based on the questions asked were used in a first step and further developed with the help of the data. The analysis focused on how inspectors put into practice their different terms of reference with regard to inspection and promotion of workplace training quality. A particular focus was on the conditions of action that are in play when interacting with trainers and apprentices or that might constrain them in their work, such as the resources at their disposal, and consequently, how inspectors might adapt their terms of reference to the conditions of action. Recontextualisation (Magnus 2019) and the distinction between input, process, and output quality served the analysis as sensitising concepts (Charmaz 2014).

The presentation of the results is organised around the four main terms of reference of inspectors: organising preventive visits, guiding firms in providing better quality training, supporting apprentices in poor training conditions, and suggesting, if necessary, the withdrawal of a training licence. The awarding of training licences to firms is not presented in detail, as this is a standardised procedure in which inspectors have little autonomy to adapt the legal framework to their conditions of action. The chosen quotations to illustrate the analysis all stem from occupation-specific inspectors, as their experiences did not differ from those of the general inspectors. They were translated from French to English and are retrievable within NVivo (attributed to one of the four terms of reference).

Findings

Organising preventive visits

According to federal law, inspection must ensure that a licenced firm complies with all training requirements (process quality). The cantonal authority thus recommends, though does not require, preventive visits to apprentices in firms, which gives inspectors a certain amount of freedom. Almost all of the inspectors felt that it was important to carry out such visits to detect potential problems at an early stage or to avoid dropouts. Inspectors argued that they are otherwise often called too late, when conflicts are difficult to resolve.

For many inspectors, however, a lack of time precluded preventive visits. Inspectors were responsible for too many apprentices, or the firms were spread over a large geographical area, making it difficult to visit them once a year. Although some of the inspectors managed to visit at least the first-year apprentices (nine inspectors out of 20) or all apprentices at least once during their apprenticeship (three inspectors), some only made the compulsory visits to firms to grant or renew a training licence (eight inspectors). These inspectors had to organise so many compulsory visits to grant training licences (up to 120 per year) that they had no time to visit the apprentices in the other firms. The inspectors interviewed would have liked to make (more) preventive visits, but were simply unable to:

It's hard to do [preventive visits] because it's the last thing we do, I'd say. Because you [...] have to look after your priorities. [...] I'm trying to tell the firm now that I want to see all the apprentices at least once during their three years. That's my goal or my challenge. And then, if it's possible, yes. [...] I come to say hello, I see how things are going for the trainer, I see the apprentices individually, and we do a debriefing to see how well or badly things are going. (Inspector in the fields of industry and mechanics)

Another reason why it is difficult to conduct regular visits, according to the inspectors, is the part-time nature of their work. The inspectors often combine inspection with responsibilities in another job, which can be difficult to manage if both workloads become intense. When the cantonal authority became aware of the lack of preventive visits, some VET managers began explicitly requiring their inspectors to visit apprentices during their first year, when dropout rates are highest. According to them, the organisation of preventive visits is not only a question of time resources but also the organisation of inspection work. Although this measure led to a slight increase in the number of preventive visits, regular visits remained difficult to organise. The rarity of preventive visits is consequential because the inspectors are often called when problems are already well established and difficult to resolve, as will be shown later.

Guiding trainers in providing better quality training

Guiding trainers to improve training quality is a central pillar of inspectors' work. This is partly because trainers must be given the opportunity to improve before a firm's licence is withdrawn, and partly because the limited qualifications among trainers were repeatedly identified as one of the major challenges for inspectors to ensure quality – challenges that inspectors actively try to address.

In the Swiss VET system, trainers must have at least two years of vocational experience in the occupation and must have completed a 40-hour training course. According to inspectors, the course does not guarantee training quality. There are several reasons for this. First, trainers can delegate training tasks to colleagues, so that apprentices are trained by employees who have not received any specific training. Second, trainers are not required to undergo further training; once they have received the certificate, they can train for decades. And third, the course provides only basic insights into the training of apprentices and often fails to cover pedagogical and human resource management issues. As a result, many trainers lack the necessary competence to guide young people:

I think that a 40-hour training course is not enough [...] to give someone all the skills they need to manage the training of young people, because things have changed a lot, society has changed, young people have changed. (Inspector in the fields of construction and building)

The most common problems that inspectors reported were related to the quality of training, such as a trainer failing to follow the training plan or sufficiently guide apprentices. It is inspectors' job to answer trainers' questions about the apprenticeship and support them in case of problems or conflicts with apprentices, while maintaining a neutral position between the two actors. But many inspectors became very involved in the guidance of trainers to compensate for their lack of qualifications. During firm visits, when issuing or renewing a training licence or when intervening after a call, inspectors often explain the official training plan and help the trainers adapt it to their firm. Some plans are very long and complex, and trainers need extra help from inspectors to implement them. Inspectors also give advice on how to provide better training and how important it is to communicate and establish a good relationship with apprentices. In this way, they go beyond their terms of reference. They also reported situations of verbal and/or psychological violence against apprentices perpetrated by colleagues or trainers. Such situations are rare, but when they occur, inspectors must stop the guidance and write a report to the cantonal authority, which can then initiate a process to withdraw the training licence.

Guiding trainers has become a priority in most inspectors' work. For this reason, many inspectors reported that, when introducing themselves to firms and apprentices, they emphasise that they are not the police, but a source of support. An inspector reported that he also had to learn that he could not just be a monitor, but had to be a supporter:

I made mistakes two to three times in the beginning, like everyone else. I was authoritarian, and that's not a solution—quite the opposite. I'm still quite firm at the beginning, but then I invite them [the trainers] to come to me if they have problems, so that I can help them, and they really appreciate that. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

However, according to the inspectors, attempts to compensate for trainers' lack of qualifications are often frustrated by trainers' working conditions, which do not offer enough time or organisational resources to ensure better training. Although trainers must follow the prescribed training plan and guide apprentices during their apprenticeship (VPETA art. 20), there is no legal regulation that specifies how much workload the firm must give to trainers. The law only specifies the number of apprentices permitted per trainer.

According to the inspectors, some firms are unaware of the time needed to plan apprentices' work, to guide them, and to monitor their progress. When evaluating whether a training licence should be issued, inspectors therefore check to see if trainers really do have time to guide apprentices and that firms do not employ apprentices simply as low-paid workers but provide a context in which meaningful training can take place. Although inspectors can recommend refusing training licences if they have doubts about the willingness or the ability of trainers and firms to guide apprentices, they regularly come across firms whose trainers are given insufficient time to fulfil their role. The following quote is from an inspector in the logistics sector, which has boomed in recent years, leading to a sharp increase in apprenticeship contracts due to labour shortages. However, also due to the shortage of labour, trainers often have little time to devote to apprentices:

Sometimes I hear the same thing over and over again: 'I don't have time; I don't have time.' And that's a problem. So, if I could wave a magic wand, it would really make everyone aware that they must respect the time given to the trainer to train the apprentice. (Inspector in the fields of industry and mechanics)

Inspectors regret that some apprentices do not receive regular and systematic assessment and feedback on their training. Although there is a practical instrument available, the training folder, in which apprentices have to document their activities and which trainers are supposed to discuss and approve twice a year, it is rarely used properly. According to the inspectors, both trainers in industries under economic pressure as well as those working in smaller firms have more difficulties following up with apprentices, as the firms are understaffed. In small firms, all the paperwork is often done by the boss. An inspector explained:

In fact, the firm should carry out interim assessments with the young person. Unfortunately, it's something that's rarely done properly. Firms that have a good structure, that are used to it, that have had several apprentices for a long time, they do these assessments. Unfortunately, it's not done systematically. (Inspector in the fields of construction and building)

In this way, inspectors confirm research findings regarding the specific challenges of delivering quality training in smaller firms (Baumeler and Lamamra 2019). However, they also point out that apprentices in larger firms can be seen as mere numbers for whom no one feels responsible. Inspectors coach trainers as much as they can in cases of poor training conditions, setting deadlines and conditions for firms to improve the learning context. They also encounter firms that refuse to accept inspectors' conditions or that only pretend to fulfil them. Inspectors must then be very engaged to insist and follow up on the improvements. In difficult situations, they involve the cantonal authority to put pressure on firms. If these measures fail, they write a report documenting the ongoing problem so that the cantonal authority can initiate a process of withdrawing the firm's training licence.

Supporting apprentices facing poor training conditions

As mentioned above, not all inspectors visit apprentices in firms or can intervene before problems become insurmountable. They are therefore dependent on trainers and apprentices calling them. However, they are often only contacted once problems and conflicts have reached an advanced stage. Sometimes, termination of the contract is unavoidable, which is frustrating:

The problem is that bosses, trainers, and apprentices alike should call me before things get too bad for them. They call me to say, 'We're terminating the contract,' but not to say, 'Come on, we've got a problem to sort out'. (Inspector in the fields of construction and building)

To prevent such situations, inspectors are required to introduce themselves at least to first-year apprentices during a vocational school or branch course to give their contact information and explain their supporting role in case of problems. Many inspectors often also take the time during these visits to inform the apprentices of their rights and obligations during the apprenticeship and about how training should be provided. They explain the competences that should be developed according to the official training plan, the role of the training folder, and that there should be at least one official meeting with the trainer per semester to evaluate and discuss their progress. In this way, they go beyond their terms of reference. The inspectors of this study also urge apprentices not to hesitate to call, even about small problems or minor questions:

In November, my colleague and I systematically visit the first-year apprentices in all classes [...] and we tell them, above all, 'Call us, even if it seems trivial to you. We'd rather answer a small question about nothing than come when everything is burnt down'. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

Although meeting apprentices during the first months of their apprenticeships has some limits, as apprentices are sometimes not yet sufficiently aware of problems that might occur during their apprenticeship, there remains a bigger barrier to inspectors' intervention. Apprentices are often afraid of losing their apprenticeship or worsening their situation; this is the main reason, according to inspectors, why apprentices are reluctant to call them.⁷ Even when apprentices do call, they often do not wish to meet with the trainer to discuss the problem:

First of all, the apprentice has to have the courage to call the inspector. And when they do, very often, I'd say 90 percent of the time, they'll say: 'I'd like to talk to you about it, but I can't tell my boss.' So, we're stuck. So, I often say: 'I agree to keep this confidential; with your agreement, I'll give you some advice once or twice, but if things don't improve, you'll have to come back to me, we'll have to organise a discussion'. (Inspector in the fields of commerce and sales)

Although inspectors (have to) respect apprentices' decision to keep their problems confidential, they encourage them to talk about it. For example, during firm visits, they always organise a meeting with the apprentice alone, so that she or he can speak freely:

When I have a meeting [...] I tell him [the trainer] clearly that I want to talk to the apprentice(s) alone. And then I receive them [...] and] at the end I always ask them if there's anything else they want to say, and I always tell them, 'If you tell me something and you don't want me to tell your boss, I'll respect your point of view. If you tell me something and you want me to go

and tell him because you don't dare, I'll do that too.' So I show them that I'm there for them. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

In general, inspectors deal with apprentices who are reluctant to talk to their trainers openly in one of two ways. Some organise a meeting with the trainer under the pretext of ensuring quality. They then steer the discussion to the relevant problem (e.g. failure to follow the training plan) and propose actions to be taken. Other inspectors feel this is deceptive and only intervene on behalf of the apprentice. One inspector explained that he seeks to avoid a 'weak position' during negotiations with trainers:

I don't do that. I went through that in the beginning. We must never put ourselves in a weak position, we must make things clear. I call and say there are things you [the apprentice] don't dare say and that I'll pass on to the trainers. Otherwise, there is the possibility [for the apprentice] to talk to the trainer and ask to call the inspector so that they can contact me. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

This second approach means that problems are only discussed with the trainer if apprentices agree to be named in the complaint; otherwise, the inspector does nothing. Apprentices are generally young and inexperienced in negotiating working and training conditions, so they often decide to keep their concerns to themselves. Their fear is warranted, because an open discussion can have negative consequences if their trainers resent the inspector's involvement.

Suggesting the withdrawal of a training licence

Although suggesting the withdrawal of a training licence is part of inspectors' mission, it is rare: a last resort. Apprentices' fear of losing their apprenticeship or having their training conditions deteriorate is one reason for this, since inspectors need apprentices' testimony. Inspectors can only suggest a withdrawal when apprentices complain about insufficient training conditions, or when the cantonal VET office asks them to investigate and write a report following a call from apprentices or their parents. Another reason is that withdrawing a training licence is a long, demanding, and open-ended process involving the cantonal VET office and lawyers. An inspector explained:

We know that some firms do not perform well. After that, it is a huge administrative task to withdraw a training licence from a firm. But then again, you need proof. There's a firm [in my occupation] whose training licence has been withdrawn. I had a case of an apprentice where things weren't going well. But the apprentice has to complain. (Inspector in the fields of construction and building)

In many cases, apprentices have already left the firm and are continuing their training elsewhere, often with the help of inspectors. They are therefore no longer afraid of losing their contract. The inspectors reported that they become involved in the withdrawal of a training licence once or twice a year. According to one of the VET managers responsible for 16 inspectors, 10 to 15 such procedures are started every year in his field, but only two or three result in the withdrawal of the training licence because firms must be given the opportunity to respond to allegations and to correct deficiencies.

The revocation of a training licence is therefore the last resort when the inspector's guidance is stymied by trainers' lack of cooperation. If the VET office decides to begin the withdrawal procedure, inspectors must also have systematically documented all deficiencies, set deadlines for correction, and followed up on the process. Otherwise, the procedure may fail. Some inspectors find it difficult to do this, as it requires writing skills, legal knowledge, and time:

You must write reports, you have to send letters, you have to build up a file, which makes us, I'd like to say, more like lawyers than people in the field and responsible for monitoring the apprenticeship system. Personally, I don't have any problems writing reports, and they are generally well received and understood. But it takes time, a lot of time. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

There is another reason why such procedures are rare. One inspector from the construction industry found it difficult to control the quality of the training process because it is impossible to visit building sites. Whether apprentices are being trained well during the day at the construction site thus remains difficult to assess. Inspectors can then be faced with a situation in which the apprentice's testimony is contradicted by the trainer's:

In the firm, I find that the most difficult element to supervise is really the guidance. Does the apprentice really have a trainer who really cares about him or her? They can tell you what they want. (Inspector in the fields of building and construction)

Poor training is therefore rarely the main reason for withdrawing a licence, since apprentices must be willing and able to provide proof and firms are given guidance and time to improve. Withdrawal procedures are thus usually initiated when there is other, more tangible evidence of non-compliance, such as breaches of labour law (e.g. unpaid wages), violations of health and safety or youth protection regulations (e.g. working hours), or when there is a cumulative effect of multiple deficiencies or infringements. When asked to describe the situation that led them to open a withdrawal case, most inspectors cited numerous serious problems:

The apprentice was treated badly: there was bullying, he wasn't learning his trade, safety measures weren't properly taken into account or respected, etc. So, the apprentice complained and it went further. (Inspector in the fields of building and construction)

Since withdrawing a training licence is a long and difficult process, inspectors and cantonal VET authorities often adopt an alternative strategy if there are persistent training quality problems. They try to convince trainers to stop training apprentices:

What is suggested to us [by the cantonal VET office] when we try to do it [open a procedure for a withdrawal], because it's also quicker, but it is also strongly suggested, is to ask the trainer to give up the training. (Inspector in the fields of hospitality and skilled trades)

While this strategy may protect apprentices from poor training conditions, it highlights the limited opportunities to penalise failure to adhere to quality standards. An older inspector also explained that for a long time, the cantonal authority had no interest in withdrawing a maximum of training licences, because in the past, when there was a shortage of apprenticeships, it was concerned that there would be enough training places available.

Summary and discussion

The educational governance approach (Langer and Brüsemeister 2019) and in particular the concept of recontextualization (Magnus 2019) make a valuable contribution to the study of inspection by providing insights into how actors at the micro level of the Swiss VET system in a French-speaking canton adapt the legal framework for inspection and quality promotion to their specific conditions of action. The analysis showed that one challenging condition inspectors face is their workload, as the cantonal VET authority assigns them too many firms and apprentices. Given the fact that inspectors often combine inspection with responsibilities in another job, organising preventive visits in firms was not always possible. This has consequences for inspection because inspectors are often called when problems are already well established. A second challenging condition inspectors face when guiding firms in providing quality training is a lack of trainer qualifications, combined with insufficient time allocated for training – both of which make it difficult to promote quality. In order to assure workplace training quality, inspectors engage in guidance whenever possible and go beyond their terms of reference. They support trainers in establishing a meaningful learning environment already when they issue training licences, not only when they are called in case of problems. In doing so, the inspectors' second mission, the promotion of quality, becomes more important than the control of quality. A third challenging condition inspectors encounter in supporting apprentices with poor training conditions is the difficulty in reaching out to them. Apprentices are often young and confined in an unequal power relationship with their employers, which can result in difficulties or fear of demanding better training conditions. Inspectors not only make their supportive role visible to apprentices, but also inform them of their rights (which is also the role of the VET school) and encourage and help apprentices to defend them. In doing so, they also go beyond what is required in their terms of reference. Finally, sanctioning firms that do not meet training quality standards also presents challenges, as it remains dependent on apprentices' testimony. Withdrawing a licence is also an arduous and open-ended process because deficiencies must prevail in a legal proceeding. This limit on the cantons' and inspectors' ability to sanction firms and to protect apprentices from poor training conditions has stimulated the strategy to convince trainers (and, respectively, firms) to stop providing training altogether.

These results reveal that inspectors do not simply impose the legal framework for inspection defined at the macro and meso levels; rather, they coordinate their practices with trainers and apprentices, taking into account their specific needs. This coordination includes inspectors' efforts to be recognised as legitimate and trustworthy actors of the VET system, who not only engage in quality control but also provide support and work towards a balance between the needs of trainers and apprentices. The adaptations inspectors make when implementing the legal framework for inspection uncover the extent of their influence within the VET system. By prioritising guidance over control and sanctions in consideration of trainers' needs and by being proactive in supporting apprentices instead of waiting for them to reach out for help (which is a common practice in other cantons), they actively shape how quality is assured and promoted. The inspectors' actions are certainly motivated by the high dropout rates the canton faces and by dual VET being less anchored in the canton.

It is important to note that some legal instructions at the federal level largely fail to achieve their objective. The legal obligation to withdraw training licences is such a complicated process in practice for cantonal VET authorities and inspectors alike that it occurs rarely. Furthermore, the resources allocated to inspectors are insufficient to fulfil the terms of reference. As a reaction to this study, the cantonal VET authority asked the cantonal education department for more resources to gradually reduce the number of apprentices per inspector from 500 to 300 and to employ more inspectors with higher workloads – for example, 60 to 80% of full-time. The pressure exerted at higher levels of the cantonal VET system proved effective, leading to the employment of more inspectors in recent years. At the same time, apprentices must be visited in their firms more regularly. Thus, the cantonal VET authority's interest in this study – namely, to improve the inspection of workplace training quality – also shapes which practices are prioritised. Although the study dates back some time and certain improvements have been implemented in the meantime, neither the federal nor the cantonal inspection systems have undergone any fundamental changes to date.

Studying inspection through the lens of recontextualisation from an educational governance perspective also contributes to discussions about models of workplace training quality (Böhn and Deutscher 2021; Fischer et al. 2014; Tynjälä 2013), which represent more of an ideal, while inspectors' conditions of action reveal how input, process, and output quality can be ensured in practice. Input quality, such as firms' infrastructural or organisational characteristics or the qualifications of trainers, is much easier to guarantee than process or output quality because a standardised process can be established to verify that firms meet all the legal requirements for obtaining a training licence. Ensuring process and output quality is a complex task, as inspectors require resources to reach out to those who may need support. Additionally, observing training processes is nearly impossible, making inspectors reliant on trainers and apprentices to identify issues and implement solutions. However, this cooperation cannot be presumed, as apprentices are in an unequal power relation with their employers and often endure poor working conditions Caprani, Duemmler, and Felder (2020). Trainers, on the other hand, are torn between their training duties and their roles as employees, frequently lacking sufficient time and qualifications to provide quality training (Lamamra and Duc 2021).

Although the findings are largely consistent with prior research on the quality of workplace training in the Swiss VET system, further investigation is needed into how both trainers and apprentices perceive the support provided by inspectors. Such an investigation would also offer a more comprehensive understanding of how inspectors coordinate with both trainers and apprentices. For example, trainers' collaboration with inspectors may vary depending on their attitude towards vocational training (Besozzi 2024), and not all apprentices may perceive inspectors as truly impartial. Moreover, further research should explore how inspectors themselves define quality in workplace training and how their subjective perceptions influence their individual approaches and decision-making (Magnus 2019).

The findings further suggest that smaller firms and sectors experiencing economic pressure tend to face greater difficulties in delivering quality training. It is already well established that dropout and success rates are closely linked to training quality (Af Burén and Schweri 2024, Negrini et al. 2016) and that these outcomes vary across sectors (OFS 2023). Moreover, small firms face distinct challenges in ensuring the

quality of their training programmes (Baumeler and Lamamra 2019). This underscores the need for further research into the specific conditions under which inspectors operate to ensure and promote training quality across different industry sectors and firm sizes.

The question also arises of whether inspectors in other Swiss cantons encounter the same conditions of action and make similar adaptations. In fact, the federal legal frameworks on training for firms and on quality assurance for cantons are the same everywhere. The inspectors' conditions of action also do not seem to be unique to this canton, or even to Switzerland. In other dual VET systems, trainers are also torn between their training responsibilities and their role as employees, and apprentices are situated in an unequal power relationship with their employer. Therefore, the observations made here may, to some extent, apply to other Swiss cantons. However, adaptations may be specific to the regional contexts, which vary significantly in terms of the availability of apprenticeship positions, young people's orientation towards dual VET, VET dropout rates, and the resources allocated to inspections. It would thus be valuable to compare how inspections are conducted across different Swiss cantons, where dual VET has different historical foundations and where cantonal VET authorities also coordinate in varying ways with trade organisations. For instance, a cantonal trade organisation in the construction sector, which has seen high contract termination rates in its VET programme, has recently criticised the limited resources allocated to inspections in Swiss-German cantons. In response, it has begun employing its own coaches to support firms in enhancing training quality (Fleischmann 2024).

It would also be valuable to compare the current observations with inspection in other VET systems, such as the German one, where chambers (rather than the state) are responsible for monitoring the quality of training (Hanf 2011). Chambers are self-administered bodies that are concerned not only with vocational training but also with the broader economic interests of firms. They also cooperate with VET commissions, which comprise representatives of employers, employees, and teachers. The Swiss system features similar tripartite commissions, but the cantonal VET authorities determine the scope and nature of their involvement in inspections. In the canton of this study, the commissions are informed when the withdrawal of a training licence is under consideration. From an educational governance perspective, it would be interesting to examine how coordination with such actors influences the inspection of workplace training quality. In any case, this study demonstrates that it is the actual practices and coordination between actors that bring governance to life – an aspect that warrants closer attention (Langer and Brüsemeister 2019).

Notes

1. In 2023, the unemployment rate, as defined by the International Labour Organization, for people aged 15–24 was 7.8% (OFS 2024b) compared to 10.6% (on average) in the OECD countries and 14.5% in the European Union (OECD 2024).
2. <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2003/674/en>.
3. <https://www.fedlex.admin.ch/eli/cc/2003/748/en>.

4. Cantons differ in size, as does the number of apprentices, ranging from about 500 to 35,000 per canton (OFS 2025).
5. Some authors do not explicitly distinguish between these factors or refer to them differently; e.g. Tynjälä (2013) uses the terms *presage*, *process*, and *product* factors.
6. Although an ethics committee was not involved, ethical standards for research were respected.
7. It should be noted that inspectors must also deal with the perception that they are not sufficiently impartial and would side with the trainer.

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